

NDAC/LO/099
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Specification of input from RGO to the Lund Double Star analysis

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document supersedes the previous specification (NDAC/LO/076) of output from the IDT Preprocessing and Location Estimator to the Double Star analysis as far as the contents and format of the tapes are concerned. The formulae for rectifying the signal parameters and calculating the weights and mean signal parameters given in NDAC/LO/076 are still valid (with a correction to eqns 2a and 2b: the exponent should be -1, not -1/2). The main modifications and additions are:

- file header record in agreement with the conventions used for the RGO/DSRI interface (Petersen, 1986 Nov 21; 1987 Mar 18);
- inclusion of the second harmonic phase for each frame in the FOV crossing (FOVC) data (NDAC/LO/095, 097);
- a first draft specification of data for individual stars (data type 'STAR') is included herewith (Section 3).

In the IDT Preprocessing, the phase of the second harmonic is obtained as

$$p2 = 0.5 * \text{ATAN2}(-b5, b4) + n * \pi \quad (1)$$

where b4 and b5 are the cosine and sine Fourier coefficients of the IDT signal. The integer n (= 0 or 1) is chosen such that p2 is non-negative. On the other hand there is no need to align p2 with the phase of the first harmonic (i.e., choosing n such that $|p2 - p1| < \pi/2$).

2. TAPE FORMAT FOR FOV CROSSING DATA

2.1. File label record

Word	Off	Len	Description
1	0	4	= 'NDAC'
2	4	4	= 'FOVC'
3	8	8	tape identifier (max 8 characters)
5	16	4	processing date in seconds since 1988.0
6	20	4	= 3 version number of file label format
7	24	4	= 8 number of words in the file label
8	28	4	= 2048 number of words in a block (max)

2.2. File header record

Name	Off	Len	Description
LHEADR	0	4	= 8 number of words in this header record
IDVERS	4	4	= 2 version number of FOVC file format
LRECFL	8	4	= 30 number of words in a FOVC record
-	12	4	= 0 indicates a fixed length record
NRECFL	16	4	number of FOVC records in the file
FMTBEG	20	4	observation time of first frame (s since 1988.0)
FMTEND	24	4	observation time of last frame (s since 1988.0)
IDFOVC	28	4	FOVC file number

2.3. Block header record

Word	Off	Len	Description
1	0	4	= 2 number of words in this block header record
2	4	4	number of FOVC records in this block

2.4. FOVC record

Name	Off	Len	Description
IDSTAR	0	4	star identification number
FMTIME	4	4	mid-time of the 1st FOVC frame (s since 1988.0)
-	8	4	micro-seconds part of the frame mid-time
WEIGHT(1)	12	2	weight of the first frame (w1) stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*w1)$
BETA3(1)	14	2	first harmonic phase (p1) of the first frame stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*p1/(2*\pi))$
BETA3P(1)	16	2	second harmonic phase (p2) of the first frame stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*p2/(2*\pi))$
.	.	.	.
.	.	.	.
WEIGHT(10)	66	2	weight of the 10th frame (w10) stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*w10)$
BETA3(10)	68	2	first harmonic phase (p1) of the 10th frame stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*p1/(2*\pi))$
BETA3P(10)	70	2	second harmonic phase (p2) of the 10th frame stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*p2/(2*\pi))$
BETA1	72	2	mean signal parameter beta1 stored as $\text{nint}(\sqrt{1e4*beta1})$
BETA2	74	2	mean signal parameter beta2 stored as $\text{nint}(\sqrt{1e4*beta2})$
BETA4	76	2	mean signal parameter beta4 stored as $\text{nint}(\sqrt{1e4*beta4})$
BETA5	78	2	mean signal parameter beta5 stored as $\text{nint}(\sqrt{1e4*beta5})$
FINF(1,1)	80	4	matrix element F11 stored as $\text{nint}(1e5*\sqrt{F11})$

FINF(2,2)	84	4	matrix element F22 stored as nint(1e5*sqrt(F22))
FINF(3,3)	88	4	matrix element F33 stored as nint(1e4*sqrt(F33))
FINF(4,4)	92	4	matrix element F44 stored as nint(1e4*sqrt(F44))
FINF(5,5)	96	4	matrix element F55 stored as nint(1e4*sqrt(F55))
FINF(1,2)	100	2	F12 stored as nint(1e4*(1.+F12/sqrt(F11*F22)))
FINF(1,3)	102	2	F13 stored as nint(1e4*(1.+F13/sqrt(F11*F33)))
FINF(2,3)	104	2	F23 stored as nint(1e4*(1.+F23/sqrt(F22*F33)))
FINF(1,4)	106	2	F14 stored as nint(1e4*(1.+F14/sqrt(F11*F44)))
FINF(2,4)	108	2	F24 stored as nint(1e4*(1.+F24/sqrt(F22*F44)))
FINF(3,4)	110	2	F34 stored as nint(1e4*(1.+F34/sqrt(F33*F44)))
FINF(1,5)	112	2	F15 stored as nint(1e4*(1.+F15/sqrt(F11*F55)))
FINF(2,5)	114	2	F25 stored as nint(1e4*(1.+F25/sqrt(F22*F55)))
FINF(3,5)	116	2	F35 stored as nint(1e4*(1.+F35/sqrt(F33*F55)))
FINF(4,5)	118	2	F45 stored as nint(1e4*(1.+F45/sqrt(F44*F55)))

3. TAPE FORMAT FOR STAR DATA

A new data type 'STAR' is introduced here for transmitting the improved star positions, photometric data, and duplicity flags calculated at RGO in the course of the mission. This file is used as input both for the Sphere Reconstitution and for the Double Star analysis. The present specification may be revised in consideration of the material actually available at RGO from the astrometric and photometric updatings.

3.1. File label record

Word	Off	Len	Description
1	0	4	= 'NDAC'
2	4	4	= 'STAR'
3	8	8	tape identifier (max 8 characters)
5	16	4	processing date in seconds since 1988.0
6	20	4	= 3 version number of file label format
7	24	4	= 8 number of words in the file label
8	28	4	= 2048 number of words in a block (max)

3.2. File header record

Name	Off	Len	Description
LHEADR	0	4	= 8 number of words in this header record
IDVERS	4	4	= 1 version number of STAR file format
LRECFL	8	4	= 16 number of words in a STAR record
-	12	4	= 0 indicates a fixed length record
NRECFL	16	4	number of STAR records in the file
TLOBS	20	4	time of last observation used for updating this star catalogue (in seconds from 1988.0)
-	24	4	= 0 (** spare **)
-	28	4	= 0 (** spare **)

3.3. Block header record

Word	Off	Len	Description
1	0	4	= 2 number of words in this block header record
2	4	4	number of STAR records in this block

3.4. STAR record

Name	Off	Len	Description
IDSTAR	0	4	star identification number
EPOCH	4	4	epoch in seconds since 1988.0
ALPHA	8	4	right ascension a (rad) at EPOCH stored as: int(a*2**24) where a is in the range 0 to 2*pi
-	12	4	remaining part ra of right ascension stored as: nint(ra*2**24) where ra = a*2**24 - int(a*2**24)
DELTA	16	4	declination d (rad) at EPOCH stored as: int(d*2**24) where d is in the range 0 to 2*pi
-	20	4	remaining part rd of declination stored as: nint(rd*2**24) where rd = d*2**24 - int(d*2**24)
DALPHA	24	4	proper motion pa (rad/s) in right ascension times cos(dec) stored as: nint(pa*2**64)+10**9
DDELTA	28	4	proper motion pd (rad/s) in declination stored as: nint(pd*2**64)+10**9
PARLAX	32	4	parallax p (rad) stored as: nint(p*2**40)+10**9
SMSTAT	36	4	starmapper status word (see below)
HMAG	40	2	magnitude H stored as: nint(H*1000) + 10000
COLOUR	42	2	colour B-V stored as: nint((B-V)*1000) + 10000
SDALPH	44	2	standard deviation sa (rad) of right ascension at EPOCH times cos(dec) stored as: nint(1e9*sa)
SDDELT	46	2	standard deviation sd (rad) of declination at EPOCH stored as: nint(1e9*sd)
NHIST(0)	48	2	histogram statistics (ibin = 0) for delta(chi2)
NHIST(1)	50	2	histogram statistics (ibin = 1) for delta(chi2)
.	.	.	.
.	.	.	.
.	.	.	.
NHIST(7)	62	2	histogram statistics (ibin = 7) for delta(chi2)

Note that the first 11 words are identical to the Star Catalogue record of the 'COOR' data type (Petersen, 1986 Nov 21), except for the SMSTAT word (= 0 in 'COOR'). The starmapper status word (SMSTAT) should contain information on the observability of the star on the starmapper and flags derived from such observations. Depending on which rejection criteria are used, SMDATA could for instance contain the following:

byte 4: INT((total number of transits detected + 9)/10) (0 to 255)
 byte 3: percentage transits rejected for attitude reconst. (0 to 100)
 byte 2: percentage transits rejected for astrometric update (0 to 100)
 byte 1: percentage transits rejected for photometric update (0 to 100)

byte 1 being the most and byte 4 the least significant part of SMSTAT.